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IMPACT EFFECTS ON CONCRETE BEAMS STRENGTHENED WITH FRP PLATES

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SUMMARY: Most of research on application of composite materials in civil engineering during the past decade concentrated on the behavior of structural elements under static loads. In engineering practice, there are many situations in which structures undergo impact or dynamic loading. In particular, the impact response of concrete beams strengthened with composite materials is of interest. This paper presents the results of an experimental investigation that was conducted to study the impact effects on concrete beams strengthened with FRP laminates. Two types of composite laminates, Carbon and Kevlar, were bonded to the top and bottom faces of concrete beams with epoxy. Five beams were tested: two were strengthened with Kevlar Laminates, two with Carbon laminates, and one unretrofitted beam as control. The impact load was applied by dropping a steel cylinder from a specified height on to the top face of the test beam. The test results revealed that composite laminates not only can significantly increase the capacity of the concrete beams to resist impact load, but also they reduce the deflection and crack width. Comparing the test results of the beams strengthened with Kevlar and Carbon laminates indicated that the gain in strength depends on the type, thickness, weight and material properties of the composite laminate.

KEYWORD: Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP), Impact, Repair And Retrofit

INTRODUCTION

Fiber composite materials have been used extensively in industries such as aerospace, automotive, chemical, shipping etc. Their applications in civil engineering were fairly limited until about ten years ago when significant attention was paid to these materials by civil engineers for repair and retrofit of structures. Because of the unique advantages of fiber composites such as corrosion resistance, high strength to weight ratio and versatility, they have been used in civil engineering projects to strengthen steel, concrete, wood and masonry structures in the last several years. Many techniques that have been implemented into retrofit design process have been based mainly on experimental research. So far, most of the research conducted on composite applications has concentrated on static and pseudo-dynamic loadings. In engineering practice, there are many situations in which structures undergo impact or dynamic loading, such as during an explosion, impact of ice load on pile structures, accidental falling loads, tornado - generated projectiles, etc. The characteristics of impact load are different than those of static and seismic loads. Since the duration of loading is very short, the strain rate of material becomes significantly higher than that under static and seismic loading. Also, structural deformation and failure modes will be different than those under static and seismic loading.

Almost all of low-velocity impact research has focused on pure composite structures. Only one study was found on impact behavior of concrete beams strengthened with composite laminates. Erki et al. conducted tests on four 8m long reinforced concrete beams strengthened for flexure [Erki and Meier 1999]. Two beams were strengthened with Carbon FRP and the other two with steel plates. Impact loading was induced by lifting one of the ends of a simply supported beam and dropping it. Strain rate of loading ranged from an average of 0.7 s^{-1} to a maximum of over

0.84 s⁻¹. They found that beams externally strengthened with CFRP laminates performed well under impact loading, although they could not provide the same energy absorption as the beams strengthened with steel plates. They investigated the failure mechanism of the test beams. Also they pointed out that additional anchoring, at least at the end of the CFRP laminates, would improve the impact resistance.

This paper discusses the test results of concrete beams strengthened with composite laminates and subjected to impact loading. Two different types of composite laminates, Carbon and Kevlar laminates, will be used in this study.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Test specimens: The test specimens included five precast concrete beams. Each beam had a 203.2 mm x 95.3 mm cross section, 1.98 m long, and had two No.3 longitudinal reinforcement ($\phi 9.53$ mm, $f_y=275.8$ MPa). The beams had no shear reinforcement. Two beams were strengthened with Carbon laminates on top and bottom faces, the other two with Kevlar laminates. One beam was not strengthened and used as control beam. Figure 1 shows the design details of the test specimens and the beam cross section. Because of the vibration induced by impact loading, the top and bottom faces of the beams will undergo cyclic tensile and compressive stresses. Therefore, composite laminates were bonded on both faces. Before laminates were bonded to concrete surfaces, beams were sandblasted down to aggregate. The surfaces of the beams and laminates were cleaned prior to bonding of laminates. Then a layer of tough epoxy was applied on one face of beam and the laminate was placed on the epoxy. After epoxy was cured, the other face of beam was worked on. Because of the uneven surface of concrete caused by sandblasting, it was impossible to measure the epoxy thickness accurately. However, on the average, the epoxy thickness was about 1.27 mm. Concrete strength was 27.6 MPa, and the elastic modulus of concrete was 24.9 GPa. The yield strength of the bars was 275.8 MPa, and the elastic modulus of reinforcement was 200 GPa. The physical and mechanical properties of composite laminates are listed in Table 1. The beams labeled TB1 and TB3 were strengthened with Kevlar laminate, TB2 and TB4 with Carbon laminate. TB5 was the control beam.

Fig. 1. Design of Test Specimen

TABLE 1 Physical/Mechanical Properties of Composite Laminates

Composite	Thickness (mm)	Weight (g/m ²)	Ultimate strain	Ultimate strength (N/mm)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)
Carbon	0.67	599	0.0139	1035	85.7
Kevlar	0.43	307	0.017	460	37.6

Test Setup and Instrumentation: All beams were simply supported. To induce impact loading a 222 N steel cylinder (127 mm diameter) was dropped on to the top surface of each beam from various heights. To prevent the beam jumping after load drop, the two ends of the beam were tied to the supports by 12.7 mm coarse threaded bars in the direction perpendicular to the supports. The ends of the beam could still rotate as beam vibrated. Two LVDTs were placed on two sides

of the beam at mid-span to measure deflection. In addition, two accelerometers were installed on the bottom face of the beam to measure the acceleration. One load cell was used at the support to measure the reaction force of the support. Residual deflection induced by impact loading was measured by a dial caliper. Twelve strain gauges were mounted on the composite laminate surfaces to monitor the distribution of longitudinal strain on the top and bottom surfaces.

For beams TB1 and TB2, the cylinder was repeatedly dropped from 1.52, 1.83, 2.44, 2.74, 3.05, 3.66, 3.96 *m* height, respectively. For beams TB3 and TB4, the cylinder was dropped repeatedly from the same height of 1.52 *m*. For beam TB5, the cylinder was dropped from 0.305, 0.61, upto 2.74 *m*.

TEST RESULTS

Reaction Force: Figure.2a and 2b show the variation of the reaction force in beams TB1 and TB2 for different drop heights ($h=1.52, 2.44, 3.05, 3.66$ *m*). Reaction force in the first half-cycle measured by load cell consists of two parts: one is the impact force directly induced by dropping cylinder, the other is the inertia force produced by the vibration of the beam. After the first half-cycle, the reaction force was caused only by the inertia force. The reaction force was increased as drop height increased. But, the frequency of vibration was reduced as the drop height increased, that means period of the beam vibration increased. Comparing Fig.2a and Fig.2b, the reaction force, inertia force and the frequency of vibration of TB2 are larger than those of TB1 for the same drop heights, this is due to the fact that the thickness and weight of Carbon laminate used in TB2 were larger than those of Kevlar laminate used in TB1. Fig.3 shows the comparison of the maximum reaction force of beams TB1, TB2, and TB5. From the first drop up to the beam failure, the maximum reaction forces of TB2 are larger than those of TB1 and TB5. This indicates that the impact and inertia forces depend on the structural stiffness, the higher the stiffness, the larger the impact and inertia forces are. The maximum reaction force of TB5 is larger than that of TB1 for the drop heights higher than 1.83 *m*. Since beam TB5 was not strengthened with composite laminates, the longitudinal bars in the beam were hardened earlier than those in TB1. So, it led to the increase of stiffness of TB5. Fig.4a and Fig.4b show the reaction force of TB3 and TB4. For these two beams, the cylinder was repeatedly dropped from a height of 1.52 *m*. The characteristics of Figs.4a and 4b are similar to those of Figs.2a and 2b. The period of vibration increased, vibration frequency decreased as the impact number increased. After ten drops, the reaction force decreased. This was caused by the formation of longitudinal cracks in composite laminate. Also, the maximum reaction force of TB4 was larger than TB3. The comparison of the maximum reaction forces of TB3 and TB4 are shown in Fig. 5. Tables 2 and 3 show the maximum reaction force for the four beams.

Table 2: Maximum Reaction Force of TB1 and TB2 (unite: *N*)

Drop Height(<i>m</i>)	1.52	1.83	2.44	2.74	3.05	3.69
TB1	3257.4	3360.6	3771.2	3683.8	4008.5	4175.8
TB2	4099.1	4615.6	5178.8	5867.9	5715.5	4897.2

Table 3: Maximum Reaction Force of TB3 and TB4 (unite: *N*)

Number of Drop	1	5	10	15	20	25	30
TB3	3498.7	3523.3	3874.6	3560.2	3414.8	3036.7	
TB4	3807.6	4053.6	4369.4	4346.8	3815.3	3803.4	3328.3

Fig.2. (a) Reaction force of TB1 for different drop heights, (b) Reaction force Of TB2 for different drop heights

Fig.3. Comparison of the maximum reaction force for TB1, TB2 and TB5

Fig. 4. (a) Reaction force of TB3 for repeated drop load, (b) Reaction force of TB4 for repeated drop load

Fig. 5. Comparison of the maximum reaction force for TB3 and TB4

Deflection: The deflection in the beams was measured by two LVDT placed symmetrically on both sides of the beam at mid-span. The average of the measured results was taken as the deflection of the beam. Figs. 6a, 6b and 6c show the deflections of beams TB1, TB2 and TB5 for different drop heights. Comparing these figures shows that the maximum deflection and vibration period of beam TB1 are larger than those of TB2, and the vibration frequency of TB2 is higher than that of TB1. The vibration period of TB5 with no strengthening with composite laminates is larger than those of TB1 and TB2. That indicates the beam TB1 and TB2 can absorb more impact energy than TB5, which is dissipated through the vibration of beams. For TB5, since the beam can not absorb that much energy, the impact energy was released through cracking and deformation of the beam. Fig. 7 shows the comparison of the maximum deflection for beam TB1, TB2 and TB5. As the impact height increases, the deflection almost linearly increases for these beams. Deflection mainly depends on the stiffness of beam, so, the stiffness of the beam is linearly reduced. In fact, change of beam stiffness under loading depends on cracking. Figs. 8a and 8b depict the deflections of TB3 and TB4 under repeated impact for a height of 1.52 m. In Fig. 8a, for the first drop, the cyclic frequency of deflection of TB3 in the first 0.1 second is less than 20 Hz. The cyclic frequency of deflection of TB4 in the first 0.1 second is more than 25 Hz in Fig. 8b. The higher cyclic frequency indicates higher flexural stiffness. Fig. 9 shows the comparison of the maximum deflection of TB3 and TB4 for repeated drops from a height of 1.52 m.

Impact loading caused cracking of concrete. At the end of the beam vibration, part of beam deflection could not recover. This deflection is referred to as the residual deflection. Concrete beam strengthened with composite laminate is not perfectly elastic, although there were no visible cracks in the concrete face after loading, the beam still showed some residual deflection due to micro-cracking. Residual deformation depends on the properties of the materials, stiffness of the beam, the distribution and width of cracks, and impact energy. Figs. 10(a) and 10(b) show the individual and cumulative residual deflections of beam TB1, TB2 and TB5, respectively. Comparing these figures, the individual residual deflection, which is the residual deflection under each impact loading, and cumulative residual deflection of TB5 are far greater than those of TB1 and TB2 for the same drop height. The residual and cumulative deflections of TB1 are larger than those of TB2. That is because the Kevlar laminate used for TB1 is lighter and less stiff than the Carbon laminate used for TB2. At $h=3.04\text{ m}$, the individual residual deflection of TB2 was larger than that of TB1, this was mainly due to shear cracks in TB2, which extended up to the interface between the concrete and the laminate.

Fig. 6(a)

Fig. 6. (a) Deflection of TB1 for different drop heights, (b) Deflection of TB2 for different drop heights, (c) Deflection of TB5 for different drop heights

Fig. 7. Comparison of the maximum deflection of TB1, TB2 and TB5 for different drop heights

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. (a) Deflection of TB3 for repeated drop load, (b) Deflection of TB4 for repeated drop load

Fig. 9. Comparison of the maximum deflection of TB3 and TB4

Fig. 10 (a) Individual residual deflection of TB1, TB2 and TB5, (b) Cumulative residual deflection of TB1, TB2 and TB5

Cracking and Failure: Flexural cracks first occurred on the bottom face of concrete, and propagated upward to the level of the neutral plane. The bending cracks could not be directly observed from the bottom and top of the concrete surface, since the composite laminates were placed on both faces. For beams TB1 and TB2, the first flexural crack was developed for a drop height of 1.83 m. For beams TB3 and TB4, the first flexural crack appeared after third drop from the height of 1.52 m. There were four or five flexural cracks in TB1 and TB3 which were strengthened with Kevlar Laminates, only one crack was observed in TB2 and TB4 with Carbon laminate. Therefore, the stiffer laminate reduced the number of cracks. The composite laminates reduced crack width significantly. Shear cracks appeared after flexural cracks. At drop height of 2.44 m, the first diagonal crack was observed in beams TB1 and TB2. For TB3 and TB4, shear crack was developed in the fourth impact from a drop height of 1.52 m. After the diagonal crack appeared, it extended quickly to the interface of concrete and laminate at the top or bottom, and extended along the interface. Local separation of concrete and laminate was then observed. The beam finally failed in shear. In regular reinforced concrete beams without shear reinforcement, the beam would fail immediately after the formation of diagonal cracks. Here, even though the shear cracks were developed, the beam could still resist further impact loading. This advantage

came from the laminate, which indirectly increased the shear capacity by preventing the cracks from opening. Longitudinal cracks were also observed in the bottom laminate (both Kevlar and Carbon). The failure of TB1 took place at impact height of 3.69 *m*, and at 3.96*m* for TB2. TB3 failed at the twenty-eighth impact, and TB4 at thirty- first impact. For the control beam TB5 without composite laminates, the bending cracks were developed at the impact height of 0.305 *m* (first impact). The shear cracks appeared at the impact height of 2.44 *m*. The final failure mode was shear failure at the impact height of 2.74 *m*.

Table 4: Impact Height of Steel Cylinder

	Flexural Cracking	Shear Cracking	Shear Failure	Composite
TB1	1.83 <i>m</i>	2.44 <i>m</i>	3.69 <i>m</i>	Kevlar Laminate
TB2	1.83 <i>m</i>	2.44 <i>m</i>	3.96 <i>m</i>	Carbon Laminate
TB5	0.305 <i>m</i>	2.44 <i>m</i>	2.74 <i>m</i>	Bare

Table 5: Impact Number of Steel Cylinder (*h*=1.52 *m*)

	Flexural Cracking	Shear Cracking	Shear Failure	Composite
TB3	3	4	28	Kevlar Laminate
TB4	3	4	31	Carbon Laminate

Analysis of Beam Behavior: The energy balance approach is considered for analyzing the impact behavior of the beams. The initial kinetic energy of the impactor is used to deform the structure during the impact. Assuming that the beam behaves quasi-statically, when the beam reaches its maximum deflection, the velocity of the impact becomes zero and all the initial energy is used to deform the beam. The energy loss due to deformation of impactor and supports is considered negligible and neglected. The overall deformation of the beam usually includes flexural, shear, and bearing deformation in the contact zone. Caprino et al (1999) have shown that, in composite structures, the energy dissipated by vibration is negligible, and the dynamic response can be simulated by static tests for sufficiently low velocity. In concrete structures strengthened with composite laminate, the deformation due to the initial impact loading is different than the deformation caused by subsequent vibration of the beam. The vibration can induce sufficient deformation in the beam to crack the concrete. In beam TB1 at the drop height of 1.52 *m*, the maximum tension strain produced by impact loading and inertia force (in first half-cycle) was 0.00267, the maximum tension strain by inertia force only (in second half-cycle) was 0.00211, this value is large enough to crack the concrete. The deflection results also proved that the inertia force alone can induce large deflections. For TB1, the deflection in the second half-cycle of vibration was about 65% of that in the in first half-cycle (see Fig. 6a), which depends on the impact energy and the stiffness of the beam.

The stress-strain relationship of any material is affected by the strain rate. When the load is applied at a fast strain rate, both the modulus of elasticity and the strength of concrete and composite increase. It has been reported that for a strain rate of 0.01/sec the concrete strength may be increased as much as 17% of the static strength. In the experiments, for example, for beam TB1 at impact height of 1.52 *m*, the average tensile strain rate of composite was 1.4 /sec, the average strain rate of concrete in compression was 0.8 /sec. These strain rates are much greater than that produced by regular loading and seismic loading. The properties of the materials therefore would be different than those from ASTM standard testing.

CONCLUSIONS

The impact tests performed in this study involved four concrete beams strengthened with composite laminates and one control beam. Two different types of laminates were used, Kevlar and Carbon. The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this study:

1. Composite laminate significantly increased the capacity of concrete beam for resisting impact loading and reduced the maximum deflection. The gain in capacity depends on the type, thickness, weight and strength of the composite laminates.
2. Dynamic response induced by impact loading needs to be taken into account, since the strain produced by inertia force is large enough to crack the concrete.
3. Reaction force of the beam varied with the thickness and weight of the laminate for the same impact energy.
4. The stiffer Carbon laminate reduced the deflection. Residual deflection of the beam was reduced with increasing stiffness.
5. Epoxy bonded composite laminates can effectively decrease the width and number of cracks.
6. Composite laminate can also increase the shear strength of the beam by preventing widening of cracks.

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